

"The Speed of Light: A Deeper Look at Einstein's Universal Speed Limit"

General relativity and speed of light are one of the most interesting topics to study and research in the field of astrophysics. Albert Einstein the author of the General theory of relativity which was a paper published by Albert Einstein originally called (Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies). Einstein worked on this idea from 1906 to 1915 and was finally published in 1916. The main idea revolves around whether time is constant or relative which means that if time is constant it should be the same for everyone living anywhere in the universe and if it is relative which means it depends on something it would be different for different observers.

What is the speed of light?

When we talk about the general theory of relativity we always think about the speed of light which is constant as we are told in our books and colleges which is true but what if I say that there is an important concept that many students lack to understand about the speed of light and general theory of relativity.

Is the speed of light really the speed of light?

Many students are taught that the speed of light is a constant value of 3×10^8 m/s, which is correct. However, what if I told you that this number represents more than just the 'speed of light'? It actually represents the universal speed limit of the universe, which is why it's important to understand it that way so to say that this is the speed of light is correct but also not correct in many cases as I described above.

Why only photons?

According to the special theory of relativity anything that has mass cannot reach this speed limit because if anything that has mass will need energy to accelerate more and more and at the universal speed limit which is $(3 \times 10)^8$ it becomes infinite so it is impossible to accelerate any thing that has mass to the universal speed limit that is why photons having zero rest mass are the only particles which can reach this speed limit.

Crossing the universal speed limit?

If we think anything that has zero mass should have an infinite speed but in our universe there is a full stop to this the laws of physics deny anything to move at infinite speed. There is a speed limit to anything that is accelerated even photons that have zero rest mass. If anything even photons could surpass this limit the laws of physics would break down if we look at the mass-energy relation provided by Albert Einstein $E=MC^2$ and put infinity in place of "c" the energy required would become infinite.

So, the next time you hear 3×10^8 is the speed of light, remember this is the universal speed limit and photons having zero rest mass can only achieve it.

About the Author: My name is Shaban Nawaz, and I am a student at Minhaj University with a deep interest in astrophysics. I am passionate about exploring the complexities of general relativity and the mysteries of the universe.

